

LWR Benchmark Testing of the Helios2 ENDF/B-VIII.1 Nuclear Data Library

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ABSTRACT

A new ENDF/B-VIII.1 nuclear data library has been generated for the Helios2 code system. The library was tested for a variety of reactor types and materials; this work focuses on applications to light water reactor criticality and depletion. Results for representative PWR and BWR facilities were generated with the new library and compared to the default Helios2 library results. The new ENDF/B-VIII.1 library performance is comparable to, but different in many respects from, the present default ENDF/B-VII.1 library. Additional testing is ongoing, but the new library appears to be suitable for inclusion in future releases of Helios2.

Keywords: Helios2, ENDF/B-VIII.1, ENDF/B-VII.1, Benchmark, LWR

1. INTRODUCTION

The Studsvik Scandpower code Helios2 code [1] is a two-dimensional lattice transport analysis system that has gained wide use for reactor fuel cycle analysis in commercial, regulatory, and research environments. It contains both Collision Probabilities (CP) and Method of Characteristics (MoC) transport solvers with a general geometry modeling capability and generalized depletion for a variety of fuel types, experimental facilities, and isotope production applications. The default nuclear data library is based upon ENDF/B-VII.1 [2] data, supplemented with other evaluated data to complete the depletion chains. A Helios2 library contains multigroup neutron, photon, and photon production cross sections; subgroup resonance data; fission neutron emission spectra; fission product yields and decay constants; and delayed neutron yields, time constants, and emission spectra.

The recent release of the ENDF/B-VIII.1 evaluated data library [3] offers an opportunity to apply the most advanced nuclear data in Helios2 and assess the potential impacts. A library based on this new ENDF data, supplemented with data from TENDL-2021 [4], was generated for testing purposes. This paper describes some of the initial testing results from this library.

2. LWR BENCHMARK TESTING

The Helios2 test suite includes models for a variety of reactor types and materials, to properly exercise the flexibility of the code. In the subsequent sections, the focus is on reactivity impacts from the E8R1 library compared to the default E7R1 library for LWR clean critical experiments and depletion benchmarks.

2.1. DIMPLE S06

The DIMPLE S06 criticals [5, 6] were conducted at the UKAEA Winfrith site during the late 1980s and early 1990s, to simulate the effects of a PWR baffle. Two configurations, each containing a cruciform arrangement of 12 PWR-type 16x16 “assemblies”, were constructed – S06A with an infinite water reflector and S06B with a 0.0267m-thick close-fitting stainless-steel slab surrounding the fuel, as shown in Figure 1. The fuel pins were 3 wt% enriched UO₂ with stainless-steel clad; the moderator was

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unborated light water at room temperature. Criticality was achieved by varying the moderator height. Measurements included criticality, axial buckling, and reaction rates for U-235, Pu-239, and U-238 fission and capture.

A one-quarter core (SE quadrant) Helios2 model was constructed for both configurations, using the measured axial buckling [6] to calculate the axial leakage effect, with reaction rate edits activated for all locations shown in Figure 1. The k -effective results are shown in Table I for the new E8R1 library and the default E7R1 library. The E8R1 library results are ~ 100 pcm lower for S06A and ~ 60 pcm lower for S06B, yielding an increase in the baffle effect of ~ 40 pcm compared to the E7R1 library. This is a combined effect from the re-evaluation of several of the stainless-steel isotopes, but especially the increases in capture and elastic scattering cross sections for Cr-50 and Fe-56. The increased capture accounts for the reactivity loss and the larger scattering cross section increases the reflector return from the baffle.

Figure 1. Core layout for S06A (left) and S06B (right) configurations; filled circles denote locations of reaction rate measurements. Diagrams from DIMPLE-LWR-EXP-002 [6].

Table I. DIMPLE S06 k -effective results for E8R1 and E7R1 libraries.

Case	Benchmark	E8R1	Δk (pcm)	E7R1	Δk (pcm)
S06A	1.0000 (0.0025)	0.99802	-198	0.99904	-96
S06B	1.0000 (0.0025)	0.99891	-109	0.99953	-47

Figure 2. U-235 fission rate comparisons to measurements for E8R1 and E7R1 libraries.

Reaction rate differences from measured values for U-235 fission (primarily thermal neutrons) and U-238 fission (primarily fast neutrons) for a trace along the center-to-SE diagonal plus the row of pins denoted by the orange arrow in the left-hand diagram of Figure 1 are shown in Figures 2 and 3. The increase in baffle reflection from E8R1 is evident in both graphs. Note that the results for case S06A are almost unchanged between the libraries.

Figure 3. U-238 fission rate comparisons to measurements for E8R1 and E7R1 libraries.

2.2. KRITZ-4

The KRITZ-4 experiments [7] were a series of critical facility measurements performed at the Studsvik site (Nyköping, SE) in 1975. The configurations used arrays of realistic 8x8 BWR fuel assemblies at elevated temperatures (19-245C). Some configurations contained burnable absorber rods and/or control blades. Borated light water was used as the moderator to help control reactivity. Criticality was achieved by varying the moderator height. Measurements included criticality, axial buckling, and normalized fission rate distributions.

Fractional (quarter or half) core Helios2 models were constructed for 47 configurations, spanning the suite of temperatures, fuels and burnable absorbers, and control modes. The measured axial buckling for each configuration was used in the Helios2 model. The k-effective results for calculations with both the E8R1 and E7R1 libraries are summarized in Table II. The average k-effective calculated from the E8R1 library was approximately 70pcm lower than that from the E7R1 library.

Table II. Summary of KRITZ-4 k-effective results for E8R1 and E7R1 libraries.

	E8R1	Δk (pcm)	σ (pcm)	E7R1	Δk (pcm)	σ (pcm)
Average	0.99792	-208	117	0.99864	-136	133
Cold Avg.	0.99788	-212	102	0.99915	-85	99
Warm Avg.	0.99836	-164	91	0.99880	-120	90
Hot Avg.	0.99759	-241	152	0.99731	-269	149

However, there were significant beneficial changes in the temperature dependence of the results. While k-effective for the cold cases was reduced by ~130pcm, the hot cases were increased by ~30pcm; this produced a clear improvement in the temperature coefficient, as seen from the trendlines in Figures 4 and 5. This indicates an improvement in the higher temperature performance of the E8R1 evaluated resonance and thermal scattering data, and is a desirable outcome for reactor analysis applications.

Figure 4. Temperature dependence of KRITZ-4 cases for the E8R1 library.

Figure 5. Temperature dependence of KRITZ-4 cases for the E7R1 library.

2.3. KRITZ-3

The KRITZ-3 experiments [8, 9] were a series of critical measurements using PWR-type fuel pins arranged in a circular pattern, performed at the Studsvik site (Nyköping, SE) in 1973. Four different core layouts were constructed (see Figure 6), containing UO_2 and MOX fuel with both small and large water holes. The moderator was borated light water at temperatures from 19–245C. A total of 89 configurations were constructed; all four layouts were calculated with and without control rods (either Ag-In-Cd or B4C). Measurements included criticality, axial buckling, and normalized fission rates; criticality was achieved by varying the moderator height and boron concentration.

Full core Helios2 models were constructed for all 89 configurations, using the measured axial buckling for each case. The k -effective results for calculations with both the E8R1 and E7R1 libraries are summarized in Table III. Average k -effective results for the UO_2 cores were slightly higher with the E8R1 library, while the MOX core results were slightly lower; the average differences were within the 2s spread of the case results for each core layout. The spread of the results for the MOX cores was generally smaller for the E8R1 library than the E7R1 library, indicating that the revised Pu isotope evaluations provide significant improvements. The spread for the controlled cases was slightly larger with the E8R1 library, while the spread for the uncontrolled cases was slightly lower. The overall

temperature trends showed no significant changes between libraries, with the trend remaining relatively flat with temperature.

Figure 6. Core layouts for KRITZ-3 configurations (from left to right) U-WH1, Pu-WH1, U-WH2, and Pu-WH2. Orange is UO₂ fuel, greens are MOX, light blue moderator, and dark blue control rod positions.

Table III. Summary of KRITZ-3 k -effective results for E8R1 and E7R1 libraries.

	E8R1 Avg.	s (pcm)	E7R1 Avg.	s (pcm)	E8R1-E7R1 (pcm)
U-WH1	1.00181	47	1.00129	38	52
U-CR1	1.00357	88	1.00309	70	48
Pu-WH1	1.00306	33	1.00324	50	-18
Pu-CR1	1.00348	30	1.00354	30	-6
U-WH2	1.00008	27	0.99951	53	57
U-CR2	1.00051	56	1.00035	38	16
Pu-WH2	1.00098	48	1.00113	71	-15
Pu-CR2	1.00056	33	1.00080	42	-24

2.4. Takahama-3 PWR

Two fuel assemblies – designated NT3G23 and NT3G24 – were irradiated in the Takahama-3 PWR for two and three cycles, respectively, from January 1990 to September 1993 [10]. Two pins from assembly NT3G23 (designated SF95 and SF96) and one pin from assembly NT3G24 (designated SF97) were subjected to post-irradiation destructive analysis to measure local burnup and isotopic concentrations, with several axial samples taken along each pin. Detailed irradiation conditions for these axial locations were provided in the reference. Pins SF95 and SF97 had initial enrichment of 4.11 wt% U-235 and pin SF96 had initial enrichment of 2.63 wt% U-235 with 6 wt% Gd₂O₃.

Single-assembly Helios2 models with reflective boundary conditions were constructed for each assembly, using the irradiation conditions provided for each sample location. Power densities were adjusted uniformly throughout the irradiation to approximately match the measured local burnup at the end of irradiation. Isotopic concentrations were calculated at the end of the defined cooling times for each sample location along each fuel pin.

Comparison of the calculated isotopic concentrations from the new E8R1 library with the default E7R1 library revealed no major trends or significant differences; the results for some nuclides improved slightly, while others slightly degraded. Comparison of the behavior of k_{∞} with burnup between the two libraries, shown in Figures 9-11 for axial sample locations near the core midplane, revealed some interesting trends. The E8R1 library results were ~150pcm higher at BOC, decreased through the first half of the first cycle, recovered through the second half of the first cycle, then slowly but steadily decreased through the subsequent cycles. There was a small (1-2%) reduction in the EOC concentrations of the main fissionable nuclides, consistent with the 100-200pcm reactivity decrement observed at EOC.

The E8R1 evaluations define a slight increase in the U-235 thermal capture cross section, an increase in the Pu-239 thermal fission cross section, and a larger increase in the U-239 capture cross section. The larger cross sections for U-235 and Pu-239 would directly decrease the concentration of these nuclides, while increased U-239 capture would cause a production diversion from Pu-239 to Pu-240 during depletion. These combined effects would cause a reduction in the EOC concentrations of the main fissionable nuclides and impact the reactivity during depletion.

Figure 7. Depletion results for UO₂ corner pin SF95 at axial location 4 (1.646m from bottom).

Figure 8. Depletion results for UO₂-Gd₂O₃ pin SF96 at axial location 4 (1.671m from bottom).

Figure 9. Depletion results for UO₂ pin SF97 at axial location 4 (1.968m from bottom).

2.5. Fukushima Daini-2 BWR

One fuel assembly, designated 2F2DN23, was irradiated in the Fukushima Daini-2 BWR for three cycles from January 1989 to November 1992 [10]. Two fuel pins, designated SF98 and SF99, were subjected to post-irradiation destructive analysis to measure local burnup and isotopic concentrations, with several axial samples taken along each pin. Detailed irradiation conditions for these axial locations were provided in the reference. Pin SF98 had initial enrichment of 3.91 wt% U-235 and SF99 had initial enrichment of 3.41 wt% U-235 with 4.5 wt% Gd₂O₃.

A single-assembly Helios2 model with reflective boundary conditions was constructed for the assembly, using the irradiation conditions provided for each sample location. Power densities were adjusted uniformly throughout the irradiation to approximately match the measured local burnup at the end of irradiation. Isotopic concentrations were calculated at the end of the defined cooling times for each sample location along each fuel pin.

Figure 10. Depletion results for UO₂ pin SF98 at axial location 5 (1.214m from bottom).

Comparison of the calculated isotopic concentrations from the new E8R1 library with the default E7R1 library revealed no major trends or significant differences; the results for some nuclides improved slightly, while others slightly degraded. Comparison of the behavior of k_{∞} with burnup between the two libraries, shown in Figures 12 and 13 for axial sample locations near the core midplane, revealed similar trends as the Takahama-3 results, with slightly larger EOC reactivity decrements.

Figure 11. Depletion results for UO₂-Gd₂O₃ pin SF99 at axial location 5 (1.189m from bottom).

3. CONCLUSIONS

A nuclear data library was generated for the Helios2 code system, based on the recently released ENDF/B-VIII.1 evaluated data library. Test calculations for a suite of light water reactor benchmarks, including both clean critical experiments and reactor depletion, were performed with the new library and compared to the existing default ENDF/B-VII.1 library. The results are comparable to those from the default library but differ in many aspects that may impact real-world applications in both positive and negative ways. The differences do not appear to be large enough to warrant major concern; additional testing of the new library is an ongoing project at Studsvik Scandpower. At present, the new library is considered to be suitable for inclusion in future releases of the Helios2 code, although there is presently no intent to replace the existing default library.

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